

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; hot 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-paced. ■

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of rice cultivars on farmers' fields in inland swamps of Sierra Leone

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Rice occupies about 75% of Sierra Leone's cultivated area. Although rice is predominantly in the uplands, the inland-valley swamps contribute a sizable area toward rice production.

To determine the performance of different rice cultivars developed at the Rokupr Rice Research Station on farmers' fields, multilocal tests were conducted under the All Sierra Leone Coordinated Agronomic Trials during

the last four wet seasons. The trials were conducted in all of the districts of Sierra Leone with a fertilizer dose of 40 kg N/ha, 40 kg P₂O₅/ha and 40 kg K₂O/ha. The cultivars ADNY 301, ROK8, and ROK6 produced an average of more than 3.5 t/ha while ROK14 and ROK4 yielded a maximum of 3 to 3.5 t/ha (see table). Besides, ROK6, ROK8, and ADNY 301 are susceptible to a large degree of variation, as much as 2.4 t/ha. The performance of CP4 and ROK5 was almost consistent.

Thus, there is a great scope to increase rice production in Sierra Leone by farmers' adoption of improved rice cultivars such as ADNY 301, ROK8, and ROK6. ■

Range of grain yield (t/ha) of different rice varieties in the inland swamp ecology.

Cultivar	Centers (no.)	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)		
			Lowest	Highest	Difference
RH2	4	16	1.2	2.9	1.7
CP4	5	18	1.8	2.6	0.8
ROK4	3	15	2.3	3.1	0.8
ROK5	4	12	1.8	2.2	0.4
ROK6 (IR5)	6	33	1.1	4.0	2.8
ROK12 (ADNY 11)	4	32	1.1	2.8	1.6
ROK8 (C13H3)	9	48	1.4	3.8	2.4
ADNY 301	7	34	2.0	4.7	2.6
ROK14 (Mange 2)	8	40	1.2	3.2	2.0

TKM9 — An improved red rice variety

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TKM9 is a red-rice derivative of the cross TKM7 (a pure line selection from Kullakar) and IR8. Developed at

Tirurkuppam, TKM9 is a high yielding semidwarf with short bold grain that matures in 110 days under wetland conditions. It is moderately resistant to fulgorids, leaf folders, sheath rot, tungro, and bacterial blight.

TKM9 can be grown like ragi *Eleusine coracana* with limited irrigation. Able to withstand drought, it can also be grown in dryland and semidryland

Performance of TKM9 at Tirurkuppam, Tamil Nadu, India

Variety	Wetland yield (t/ha)	Yield increase over IR20 (%)	Yield (t/ha) with limited irrigation	Increase or decrease (%) compared with CO34
TKM9	5.2	44.4	2.9	81
ADT31	4.3	19.4	1.9	19
CO34	4.1	13.9	1.6	—
IR20	3.6	—	0.7	56

conditions. Its highest recorded yields are 5.2 t/ha under wetland and 2.9 t/ha under limited irrigation – superior to

those of the other varieties tested (see table). Red rice is preferred in southern Tamil Nadu. ■

A breakthrough in the ceiling grain yield of ponlai rice

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The grain yield per unit area of ponlai rice in Taiwan is said to have approached a ceiling; during the past decade the yield increase of elite entries in regional tests has been less than 5%. The incorporation of the semidwarf plant type into ponlai varieties is considered necessary for further yield increases.

The new variety Tainung 67 has given a breakthrough in grain yield. It probably inherited its semidwarf plant

type from Taichung Native 1 through a “bridge” variety, Taichung Shi 138 (later named Taichung 187).

Tainung 67, a selection from the cross Taichung Shi 138/2* Tainung 61, outyielded the control variety by 9% in the first crop and by 14% in the second crop in regional yield tests at 8 locations in Taiwan from 1977 to 1979. The variety is particularly adapted to Hsinchu, Tainan, and Taitung districts (see table). Its high yield potential was also confirmed in local trials in Taipei, Hsinchu, and Taichung districts. Tainung 67 showed a relatively low regression coefficient of entry means on environment means of grain yield in the regional yield tests (see

figure). A sister line, TNGY-WF5, showed an even lower regression coefficient, but with a lower yield potential.

The growth duration (transplanting to harvest) of Tainung 67 is about 120 days in the first crop and 100 days in the second. It is relatively lodging resistant and responsive to nitrogen fertilizer. In the uniform disease nurseries, Tainung 67 showed blast resistance similar to that of Tainan 5 and fair resistance to bacterial blight. It is relatively tolerant of the brown planthopper and sclerotial stem rot. Its milled rice quality meets local consumer requirements. In 1978 the new variety was planted in 101,000 ha in Taiwan, mostly in Hsinchu, Taichung, and Tainan districts. It is expected to be more widely planted in 1979. ■

Grain yield of Tainung 67 and percentage of yield increase over the control variety in 1977–79 regional tests at 8 locations in Taiwan.

Location	Tainung 67				Control variety
	1st crop yield (t/ha)	Increase (% over control)	2d crop yield (t/ha)	Increase (% over control)	
Taipei	6.0	7	4.7	8	Taipei 309
Hsinchu	5.2	15	4.8	22	Hsinchu 56
Taichung	7.4	8	6.0	18	Tainan 5
Tainan	1.0	13	4.5	20	Tainan 6
Kaohsiung	5.3	2	3.1	11	Kaohsiung 139
Taitung	5.7	20	4.9	23	Taitung 27
Hwalien	5.1	18	3.9	9	Tainan 5
Lotung	4.7	-4	3.7	5	Tainan 5

IR2053-206-1-3-6, a new rice variety for the Sudan Gezira

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The line IR2053-206-1-3-6 has performed well in field experiments and observational nurseries at the Gezira Research Station (GRS) from 1975 to 1978. The line, introduced from IRRI in 1975, is from the cross IR1416-131-5/IR22//C4-63. Its plant type, growth duration, yield, and grain quality are superior to those of the rices currently grown in the Gezira. At GRS, its yields were as high as 8.6 t/ha and averaged 6.9 t/ha in farmers' fields. GRS established direct seeding as the standard cultural practice for IR2053-206-1-3-6.

In an ARC meeting at Wad Medani on 20 February 1979, the Sudan Technical Subcommittee for Variety Release unanimously accepted the release of IR2053-206-1-3-6 as a rice variety for the Gezira. ■

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

Grand mean yield (t/ha) of rough rice and regression coefficient (bi) of entry means of environment means of 14 entries in 1977II-1979I regional yield trials of ponlai japonica rice varieties at 8 locations in Taiwan. TNGY = Tainung yuh, CNY = Chianung yuh, TPY = Taipei yuh, HCY = Hsinchu yuh, TCY = Taichung yuh, NKY = Nankai yuh, KHY = Kaohsiung yuh, TTY = Taitung yuh, HLY = Hwalien yuh. Taiwan.